

////////////////////////////////////

GOING RUSH: A STUDY FOR REINVENTING THE LOCAL RUSH-WEAVING INDUSTRY

Fang-Wu Tung

National Taiwan University of Science and Technology
fwtung@ntust.mail.edu.tw

ABSTRACT

- This design-led research explores how leveraging design creativity can reveal new opportunities for local rush-weaving crafts of Yuan Li in Taiwan, expanding the market potential of the crafts through the development of new products. This study matched design students with local craftspeople to form a cooperative team to expand the craft vocabulary and tapping contemporary markets. The design process in the study was implemented in four phases, including design research, design strategy exploration, design execution, and design promotion. Seven works were delivered under four design concepts including diversity and authenticity, emphasis of the aesthetics of rush weaving, introduction of rush-weaving to other industries, and product design based on rush rather than rush-weaving. This research is conducted with the consideration of the alliance of craft and design as a fulfilling learning experience, where both sides can exchange learning information to enhance their professional capability. Drawing from this collaborative experience, this study highlights the value of collaborative approaches to craft and contemporary design practice, and outlines design principles such as presenting the aesthetics of crafts, reviving old craftsmanship, and discovering the uniqueness of local industries, which serve as valuable references for design education and practice.

Keywords: Design, Rush weaving, Local Craft, Cultural Product

INTRODUCTION

Local crafts such as cultural heritages reflect a relationship between humans and their environment

within their historical, cultural, and social contexts. Jaykar (1989) indicated, "craft is an economic activity before it is a cultural activity. The center of the development process is marketing." Craftspeople are skilled at using local materials to create products whose production and sales can generate income. Once similar products manufactured with alternative or newer materials were introduced into the market, the demand for traditionally crafted products declined sharply. In addition to diminished markets, factors such as unfamiliarity with market tastes, needs, and limited access to working capability have often rendered these crafts unavailable to cope with market demands. Regarding the preservation of local traditional crafts, more effort is necessary to help revive these crafts and contribute to self-sustained local communities. Developing cultural products based on traditions and cultural heritage has been viewed as a means to promote and sustain local economic development (Santagata, 2000). Local crafts, such as a type of craft of a specific cultural heritage (Moreno et al, 2004), can be used as a strategic asset for local communities by providing them with opportunities for economic participation, the ability to create small-sized businesses, and the sustainability of local or community industries. While local cultural heritage receives attention, areas experiencing economic downturn or local crafts being neglected hence face great prospects for economic revival. The concept of the "One Village One Product" (OVOP) or "One Town One product" (OTOP) movement, originating from Japan and being promoted in numerous Asian countries, is meant to encourage local residents to manufacture distinctive products through the use of locally available resources and resident skills to introduce the products into the local or global market (Rana, 2008). As globalization increases standardization and homogenization, a growing

market searching for unique and authentic products has emerged, creating a niche for creativity, innovation, and uniqueness (McIntyre, 2010). Designers can adopt crafts as a genre of material cultural heritage to create product differentiation. For consumers, handmade crafted products using natural materials and employing traditional craftsmanship prove a delight and demonstrate uniqueness compared to mass-produced goods. The crafted products are compelling, distinctive, and welcomed in the modern market. The market for crafted products has the potential to stretch across a number of markets, from accessories to home-ware and other categories beyond the traditional segments. In this context, the demand for appropriate design is increasing, opportune on seeking new economic growth for traditional craft industries (UNESCO, 2005). Furthermore, designers face a new challenge and direction of regarding local cultural idiosyncrasies as a source of inspiration and congealing cultural symbolism in products and imbuing them with authentic character to enhance place-specific competition (Scott, 2004). This implies that designers must now design products reflecting their own culture and environments, which can also distinguish their products from others in the market. In summation, design can function as a strategy to stimulate local craft industries, and the crafts can be integrated into product design to attain differentiation with the authentic expression of creativity. This study thus grouped design students with rush weavers to explore the possibilities that rush-weaving offers, developing innovative product tapping of contemporary markets. This study can be considered a new attempt at introducing local craft techniques to the curriculum of product design. By combining the design abilities of students and the rush-weaving knowledge of Yuan Li, the objectives of this research are as follows: (1) develop new product lines to meet modern market demands; (2) gain an understanding of the contributions industrial designers can make to the rush-weaving community; and (3) explore the integration of local crafts into design education.

RUSH WEAVING IN YUAN LI

Rush weaving is Yuan Li's century-old indigenous craft industry. Weaving made use of stalks of rush,

producing mats, hats, and handbags. The rush-weaving industry has power over local economy, culture, and life. A golden age of exporting rush-woven hats and mats abroad was present. During this golden age, almost every household was involved in rush weaving and contributed to the prosperity of the local industry. After a period of prosperity, akin to numerous other local craft industries, due to changing times and industrialization, the market for rush weaving gradually eroded because of the availability of diverse alternatives, rendering the craft unsustainable. In Yuan Li, the craft of rush weaving was transferred down generationally without institutionalized teaching. In this manner, rush weavers were taught to produce rush-woven hats and mats with specific techniques because the two items had been major products of the past; craftspeople are thus accustomed to using their skills to make certain products in similar styles, rendering their products less appealing to modern tastes. Though machine-made rush-weaving products are replacing hand-made products, their overall quality and style are inferior. However, the lower price of machine-made products is a threat to handmade rush weaving (Chang, 2002; Yang & Yeh, 2007; Lu, 2010). Designers can therefore serve as an interface to link tradition and modernity, helping match rush-woven products to the demands of modern societies. Furthermore, the design intervention could bring new concepts to enhance their performance regarding techniques, materials, and processes. This study hence attempted to bridge the rush-weaving craft and design to enhance design and creativity, enabling people to grasp the potential in the rush-weaving craft, consequently effectuating the sustainability of the local industry. Concerning craft preservation, this study examines modes of expanding the range of application by utilizing the craft and rush material to reach contemporary markets. In addition to exploring what contributions designers can make to revive the rush-weaving industry, this study provides a learning experience by integrating local material and traditional craft into the design curricula. The rush and rush weaving composed in Yuan Li possess uniqueness worth examining further, as follows:

- Eco-friendly: Rush is a green material, derived from the cyperaceae perennial herb, with an

average length of 1 to 2 m. The rush from Yuan Li is planted in paddy fields and can be harvested twice or thrice annually. Unlike the round-shaped rush from other areas, the rush from Yuan Li has a triangular shape with tough fiber, and is uneasily broken or discolored. Rush-woven products made in Yuan Li are thus quite durable. These features support the fact that the rush is a great green-design material that is friendly to the environment. Because eco products are becoming dominant trends in the international market, this type of eco focus creates a niche market for products composed of rush.

- **Natural characteristics:** The stomas and gaps among cells of triangle-shaped rush from Yuan Li are larger compared to that of other species. Its semi-open stomas have characteristics of moisture absorption, air permeability, and deodorization. Moreover, it emits a distinct pleasant aroma.
- **Delicate Touch:** The texture of rush-woven products is highly delicate, and the secreted plant wax can also smoothen the surface to be more delicate; rush-woven products could therefore be comfortable to the touch of users, and its texture is vastly superior compared to other grass-woven products.

METHODOLOGY

A cooperative design-led research was conducted between university students majoring in Industrial Design and rush-weaving craftspeople from Yuan Li. This collaborative experience provided students with a chance to learn the related local materials and crafts. By integrating traditional crafts into the curriculum of product design, students gained hands-on experience by working with craftspeople and obtaining their tacit knowledge. With the participation of seven design students and five rush-weaving craftspeople, the study occurred over an approximate period of nine months. This study was conducted and implemented in four phases, including design research, design strategy exploration, design execution, and design promotion, as shown in Figure 1. The design process is described as follows:

Figure 1. The Design Process

DESIGN RESEARCH

In the early stages, field studies in Yuan Li were essential for students to understand the local context and to assess the craft techniques, materials, products, markets, resources, traditions, and most importantly, the bottlenecks. Through field studies, students could interact with the rush weavers directly, by helping build a partnership between the both sides. Furthermore, activities associated with design research, such as material exploration, market research, interpretation, and analysis required implementation. Results of design research enabled participants to identify artisan skill bases, strengths, and bottlenecks in the functions of rush weaving as a viable economic activity.

DESIGN STRATEGY

According to the results of design research, the internal strengths of rush weaving involve the artistic quality and delicate touch, the natural characteristics of rush, and its rich resources. The internal weaknesses involve insufficient craftspeople, little product range, and limited design skills for innovation and product development. Regarding the opportunities and threats arising from external environments, the former is referred to as the emerging market for authentic products, the eco chic trend, and environment-friendly awareness. The latter is mainly from the shrinkage of the original market and the increasing competition from low-cost machine-made grass-woven products.

Design could therefore contribute to the rush-weaving industry by designing new product lines to enhance traditional items to appeal to prospective clients, introducing appropriate manufacturing processes and other materials to reduce drudgery, and creating visibility for the craft. Through the collaboration, transferring design knowledge and information to the members of the community is crucial to helping the community become self-sustainable. Therefore, the community's capability of production or their access to resources, such as manufacturing methods or materials, should be

considered. Scott (1996) devised three characteristics of successful cultural products, which serve as useful references to plan design strategy, as follows: (1) The products are of high quality and diversity, and the producer displays a capacity for constantly changing design configuration over time; (2) The producers are innovative in all dimensions of their business activities; and (3) Their products enjoy strong collective reputation effects derived from their places of origin. Based on the aforementioned research and analysis, four design strategies for product design for rush weaving were established, as follows:

- Diversity and authenticity
- Emphasis of the aesthetics of rush weaving
- Introduction of rush-weaving to other industries
- Product design based on rush rather than rush-weaving

DESIGN EXECUTION

In the design execution stage, designer students played a chief role in conceptualizing the design and devising the form for an emerging product. During this time, craftspeople helped students identify and correct mistakes related to the manufacturing difficulties of rush weaving. A range of feasible product developments for each design strategy was delivered after an iterative process. Seven design concepts in compliance with the aforementioned design strategies are listed as follows:

Diversity and authentic

One approach to achieve successful cultural products requires producers to deliver products consistent in high quality and diversity. A series of bracelet designs based on existing craft techniques was proposed, as illustrated in Figure 2. The tube-shaped body of the bracelet is woven in the same fashion as when weaving the handle of rush-woven bags. By combining different woven bodies with various types of materials, diverse bracelet design can be created. The combination of rush weaving with other materials, such as metal or plastic, enables the bracelet to adopt a modern aesthetic with more ease compared to a product composed only by rush weaving. The artistic quality and handmade texture

of rush weaving can be applied to accessories particularly in the use of emphasizing personal styles.

Figure 2. Design Work 1- A series of bracelet designs based on existing weaving techniques

Emphasis of the aesthetics of rush weaving

Compared to traditional rush-woven products such as hats and mats, the development of new rush-woven product lines can create access to new markets. The aesthetics and characters of rush weaving can promote products that are simultaneously decorative and functional, especially for home accessories and décor. Rush-woven products can enhance artistic quality and natural feelings in daily life. Two works were created for the design strategy: a radio and a lamp. By integrating the rush-weaving craft with such products, a unique, natural, and aesthetic style was developed. This unique style not only introduces local craftsmanship into new markets, it also helps distinguish radios and lamps from other domestic products, drawing the attention of consumers. As illustrated in Figure 3, the design features of this work are in the lighting changes formed by the pattern of rush weaving and the gaps made by the metal material. By adding the metal material, a rush-woven product can also attain a modern look and reduce the demand for labor force.

Figure 3. Design work 2- A lamp

By rush weaving, the radio appears different from typical radios (seen in figure 4). The weaving pattern

in different densities of meshes, used for the surface for speaker cloth, could present the characteristics of the rush-weaving craft. The radio knobs are also covered with rush-woven material, providing a delicate touch experience for the user.

Figure 4. Design work 3- A radio

Introducing rush weaving to other industries

Introducing rush weaving to other industries can expand the application of the craft industry. Regarding the design strategy, an attempt was made to incorporate rush weaving with consumer electronic products. In Taiwan, numerous companies have found differentiating their consumer electronic products based on performance difficult, since the maturing of technological development. Rush weaving could transform electronic products into "eco chic" due to the sustainable raw materials, natural characteristics, and artisan quality. The figure 5 demonstrates that the rush-woven material could be used as parts of electronic products, such as earphones, computer mice, and electronic books that are normally used by users for extended time periods, enabling users to experience the natural characteristics of rush-woven material. Following the trend of green design, no greater time exists for applying rush to the design of consumer electronic products. Doing so could distinguish products from competitors on the market greatly, and enhance their competitiveness as a consequence.

Figure 5. Design work 4- A pair of earphones. Design work 5- A computer mouse. Design work 6- An e-book (left to right)

Designing products based on rushes without weaving techniques

To solve the lack of rush weavers and make use of the rich rush resources in Yuan Li, this study developed product design based on the local raw material. As shown in Figure 6, the Triangle-Rush Stool presents two approaches to managing rushes to produce a stool. Triangle rushes can be used for stool surfaces by using both slicing and wrapping techniques. The former involves affixing bunches of triangle rushes in a piece of concave wood before cutting them to form a stool surface. The process revealed the triangle sections of Yuan Li's rushes, and the surface presented a beautiful pattern. This wrapping method involves removing fibers from triangle rushes, leaving only the skin, which was used for wrapping around the rim of the concave wood, giving off natural tones due to the uneven and natural coloration of triangle rushes, shown in Figure 7.

Figure 6. Design work 7- A Stool

Figure 7. The stool surfaces made by using slicing and wrapping techniques

DESIGN PROMOTION

Attending relevant exhibitions and design competitions is crucial for design promotion, to inform and broaden the awareness of the public audience. To enhance visibility of the craft industry,

the design works have been displayed in exhibitions to increase publicity. This study attempted to draw attention from potential consumers and business partners through these exhibits. In addition, these works also won the recognition of design contests, such as the lamp, Design work 2, where the work was awarded “Good Design” by the Taiwan Design Alliance in 2010. This work was selected to be exhibited at the Taipei Flora Expo in 2010-2011. The stool, Design work 7, won a prize in the OTOP design contest held by the Taiwanese government, and will be commercialized and sold in the channel of distribution and marketing of OTOP products, consequently helping the development of the craft business.

DISCUSSION

This project aimed to revitalize Yuan Li’s rush-weaving industry, which involved skill-based knowledge and accumulated experiences that cannot be transmitted explicitly, though they can be transferred to other individuals through a collaborative and interactive process with craftspeople (Asheim et al, 2007). This study thus matched design students with local craftspeople to form a cooperative team working together to acquire the potential and bottlenecks of the rush-weaving industry. Teaming up design students and craftspeople enables them to integrate diverse knowledge sets and skills, allowing for the creation of a rich novel combination of ideas (Alves et al., 2007). Exposing designers in the local context is essential for and acquiring at least a basic familiarity with the material of rushes and technical skills to avoid developing irrelevant product design. This collaboration did not only focus on creating more products, but obtained more insights and possibilities regarding how industrial designers can contribute to revitalize a downward local craft industry. Drawn from the collaborative experience, this study outlined the following design principles for developing rush-weaving crafts, including highlighting the aesthetics of the rush-weaving craft, innovation based on the revival of existed techniques, expanding the opportunities of craft industry through cross-field alliance, and promoting local material as place-specific identity, which serve as valuable references for relative design practices.

HIGHLIGHTING THE AESTHETICS OF THE RUSHWEAVING CRAFT

Since the industrial revolution, traditional rush-woven items have been composed by machines or further replaced by other materials or synthetic textiles. However, the rush-weaving craft conveys distinct aesthetic qualities, natural texture, and production value, which cannot be replaced. Thus, modern rush-weaving craft items are not only utilitarian, but their aesthetics are also a significant for the design. To promote the rush-woven products, bringing the aesthetics and features of the rush-weaving craft and into product design is essential to satisfy both aesthetic and functional needs. Furthermore, emphasizing the aesthetics of rush weaving can encourage more creativities and innovations, which benefit promoting skilled laborers and artisans.

INNOVATION BASED ON THE REVIVAL OF EXISTED TECHNIQUES

Design-based innovation occurs by using existing knowledge (Pannozzo, 2007), which also applies to craft industries. To drive innovation of the rush-weaving industry, existing craft techniques and experiences are essential for generating new possibilities. Furthermore, the use of old techniques could effectuate the cooperation between designers and craftsmen. The design concept of bracelets was derived from weaving techniques for producing tube-shape handles of rush-woven bags. This approach encourages craftspeople to create diverse designs via a variety of already-familiar weaving techniques. Infusing old techniques with new lifestyles benefit a positive cooperation model, through which design students understand and explore application aspects of traditional craftsmanship. Craftsmen can also review their own skills and creations from a different viewpoint, and thus be inspired to develop more creative designs. The revival of existing techniques enables rush weavers to deliver innovation designs on their own, leading to the sustainability of the cultural industry.

DISCOVERING AND MANIFESTING PLACE-SPECIFIC IDENTITY

A chief reason why Yuan Li’s rush-woven products are reputed is due to the good quality of their

triangle-shape rush, which can be used to manufacture more delicate and durable products compared to others. The authenticity and quality of Yuan Li's triangle rush serve as an identity related to that locality and has potential to achieve competitive advantage. The rush-woven products, however, can hardly show the difference between triangle rush and other rush types. Manifesting this difference by product design is an effective approach to enable consumers to recognize the product as unique to its specific geographic characteristics, which helps consumers connect the products and the authentic qualities of Yuan Li, forming a regional identity. This study recognized the unique feature of triangle rush in Yuan Li before integrating this difference into the design work, the Triangle-Rush Stool. The stool surface formed by a section of triangle rush manifests and emphasizes the special origin of the material from Yuan Li. This design shows a potential approach to create innovative products based on Yuan Li's rush to build their place-specific identity. Regional identity refers to the authenticity of a location. The uniqueness varies from according to region, and therefore, designers must unveil the authenticity or significant attributes of the local industry to manifest the uniqueness as regional identity through design. The design creates a link between the regional identity and the authenticity of the local industry, thereby contributing to the promotion and development of the local industry.

EXPANDING THE OPPORTUNITIES OF THE CRAFT INDUSTRY THROUGH CROSS-FIELD ALLIANCE

The cross-field alliance has the potential to expand the application of rush weaving to other industries. From this perspective, this study used rush as an optional material for designing electronic consumer products to improve user experiences. Prye (1968) suggests that the role of the craft and its attributed status is related to its ability to exist as a high-quality complement to industrial and technological advances. Doing so not only extends the potential of rush weaving, but this design can also be an added value of quality and naturalness for electronic consumer products. This study applied rush weaving to the surface design of products, such as earphones, electronic books, and computer mice, which might

receive the attention and interest of related manufacturers, and contribute to the cross-industry alliance for the rush-weaving industry in Yuan Li. The design might enable manufacturers to differentiate their products and gain competitiveness, which could help them avoid cost competition.

CONCLUSION

Design is regarded as a means to contribute to local regeneration and economic development (Bell & Jayne, 2003). Designers working with craftspeople could exchange knowledge of traditional craft skills to deliver products that meet modern market demands. In addition to delivering new products, a chief objective of the collaborative project is to inspire craftspeople to further their own innovations, and not to stunt them into passive replication. The experiences acquired from this collaboration could inspire craftspeople to view their skills, materials, and techniques from a fresh angle, and use these resources to create products from their own designs. The knowledge transmission is crucial to building a self-sustainable community.

The collaboration in this study is a learning experience for both sides. In addition to benefiting local development, integrating traditional crafts and local materials into design curricula can enrich student knowledge through the process of discovering potential skills and materials that they are unfamiliar with. Walter Gropius, the founder of the Bauhaus, believed that the best approach to training young designers should comprise courses that free their individual creative ability and provide them with the knowledge regarding a range of materials (Gropius, 1948). Craft involves building skills and knowledge, referring to technique, material, and traditional aspects. Design educators should recognize the potential of traditional crafts as a resource for learning and guide students to appreciate the values of traditional crafts not only as a process or product, but also as a cultural practice with relevant functions in the community and society. Therefore, introducing traditional crafts to the design curricula of academic programs provides students with an opportunity to learn how to utilize local materials in crafted approaches and broaden their perspectives. To appreciate the importance of local cultural industries in economic development,

design education should respond to this trend by placing students in unique positions to join emerging Industries.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This material is based upon work supported by the National Science Council of the Republic of China under grant NSC 98-2218-E-239-001-. The author thanks all participants in this study for their invaluable contribution.

REFERENCES

- Alves, J., Marques, M. J., Saur, I., and Marques, P. (2007). Creativity and Innovation through Multidisciplinary and Multisectoral Cooperation. *Creativity and Innovation Management*, Vol. 16, No. 1, 27-34
- Asheim, B.T., Coenen, L., Vang, J. (2007): Face-to-Face, Buzz and Knowledge Bases: Socio-Spatial Implications for Learning, Innovation and Innovation Policy. *Environment & Planning C*, Vol.25, No. 5, 655-670
- Bell, D., Jayne, M. (2003), Assessing the role of design in local and regional economies, *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, Vol. 9, No. 3, 265-284
- Chang, C.J. 2002, *Straw hats & mats in Taiwan (臺灣帽蓆)*, Taipei: SMC Publishing Inc.
- Cooke, P., Leydesdorff, L. (2006), Regional Development in the Knowledge-Based Economy: The Construction of Advantage. *Journal of Technology Transfer*, Vol. 31, 5-15
- Gropius, W. (1984) Teaching the Arts of Design. *College Art Journal* . Vol. 7, 160-62;
- Huber, M., Williams, A., Shaw, G., (1992) Culture and economic policy: a survey of the role of local authorities", WP5, Tourism Research Group, Department of Geography, University of Exeter, Exeter
- Jaykar P. (1989) Speech at crafts council of India seminar, NID
- Lin, R. T. (2007) Transforming Taiwan Aboriginal Cultural Features into Modern Product Design: A Case Study of a Cross-cultural Product Design Model, *International Journal of Design*, Vol. 1, No.2, 47-55.
- Lu, J.H., 2010, *Documentation: Rush-weaving craftsperson (紀錄蘭編人)*, Taiwan rush weaving association
- McIntyre, M. H. (2010) Consuming Craft: the contemporary craft market in a changing economy [Internet]. Crafts Council. Available from: [Accessed: 10th May 2011].
- Molotch, H. (2002) 'Place in product. *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research*, Vol. 26, No. 4, pp. 665-688
- Moreno Y.J., Santagata W., and Tabassum A. (2004) Material cultural heritage, cultural diversity, and sustainable development. Paper presented at the 13th annual conference of ACEI, June 3-5, Chicago, USA
- Pannozzo, A. (2007), The (Ir) relevance of Technology: Creating a Culture of Opportunity by Design. *Design Management Review*, Vol. 18, 18-24
- Prye, D (1968) *The Nature and Art of Workmanship*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press
- Rana, E. C. (2008), Sustainable Local Development Through One Town One Product (OTOP): The Case of OTOP Movement in Mindanao, Philippines, *Journal of OVOP Policy*, 1, 31-38
- Santagata, W. (2002) Cultural districts, property rights and sustainable economic growth. *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research*, Vol. 26, 9-23
- Scott, A. (1996) The craft, fashion and cultural-products industries of Los Angeles: competitive dynamics and policy dilemmas in a multi-sectoral image production complex, *Annals of the Association of American Geographers* , Vol. 86, No. 2, 306-323
- Scott, A. J. (2004) Cultural-products industries and urban economic development - Prospects for growth and market contestation in global context. *Urban Affairs Review*, Vol. 39, No.4, 461-490
- UNESCO, (2005) *Designers Meet Artisans: A Practical Guide*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press
- Yang, M.Y., Yeh, W.H. (2007) Promoting Community's Crafts and Developing Cultural Commodities: Yuan Li Triangle Rush Weave as an Example (社區工藝推廣與文化商品發展—以苗栗苑裡山腳社區的蘭編品為例), *Proceedings of 2007 International Conference on Culture Goods Design*, June 23, Yunlin, Taiwan, 99-109